

Synthesis of Bis-Thiazolidone and Bis-Thiohydantoin and their Derivatives from *m*-Phenylene Diamine

T. E. ACHARY, C. S. PANDA AND A. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University and Department of Chemistry,
G. M. College, Sambalpur.

Manuscript received 27 May 1972; accepted 4 July 1975

2,2'-(*m*-phenylene) bis-2-imino 4-thiazolidone (I), 3,3'-(*m*-phenylene) bis-thiohydantoin (II), their arylidene derivatives (III and IV) and tetrabromo compounds have been synthesised from *m*-phenylene diamine as possible bactericides and fungicides.

IN view of the close relationship between thiazolidones and thiazolidine, whose moiety is present in penicillin and the reported use of thiazolidones and thiohydantoin compounds as antibacterial¹ and antifungal² agents it was of interest to explore the synthesis of bis-thiazolidone, bis-thiohydantoin and their derivatives from *m*-phenylene-diamine.

Aqueous solution of *m*-phenylene-diamine dihydrochloride when heated with ammonium thiocyanate gave the bis-thiourea; which on condensation with monochloro acetic acid in alcohol and anhydrous sodium acetate furnished the bis-thiazolidone (I). On the other hand when the condensation was carried out in the medium of pyridine bis-thiohydantoin (II) was obtained.

Both the ketomethylene compounds (thiazolidone and thiohydantoin) have been condensed with various aromatic aldehydes and the resulting diarylidene compounds (III and IV) have been brominated.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and IR spectra of the compounds were taken on KBr discs.

m-(Thiourea)-phenyl-thiourea

This was obtained by refluxing *m*-phenylene diamine dihydrochloride (10.8 g) with ammonium thiocyanate (23 g) on a water bath for 4 hr and crystallising the solid obtained with DMF. Yield 60%, m.p. 203°. (Found: S, 27.16; C₈H₁₀N₄S₂ requires S, 27.32%).

2,2'-(*m*-phenylene) bis-2-imino 4-thiazolidone

A mixture of the above thiourea (0.1M) monochloro acetic acid (0.2M) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.1M) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. After cooling it was poured into water and the solid obtained was washed with hot water and finally crystallised from acetone alcohol mixture (1:1). Yield 56%, m.p. >250°. (Found: S, 20.36; C₁₂H₁₀N₄S₂O₂ requires S, 20.91%) λ_{max} (cm⁻¹); 1730 (C=O), 1405 CH deformation in CH₂, 1640 C=N stretching, 3400 (NH) broad

3,3'-(*m*-phenylene)-bis-thiohydantoin

The above thiourea (0.1M) was treated with monochloro acetic acid (0.25M) in pyridine (10 ml) and warmed till the exothermic reaction takes place. It was cooled, treated with alcohol (20 ml) and refluxed for one hour. The grey coloured solid obtained was crystallised from aq. DMF. Yield 52%; m.p. >250°. (Found: S, 20.68; C₁₂H₁₀N₄S₂O₂ requires S, 20.91%) λ_{max} (cm⁻¹); 1770 (C=O) 3300 (NH).

Bis-arylidene thiazolidones (Table 1)

The thiazolidone (0.01M), aldehyde (0.01M) and anhydrous NaOAC (0.02M) in HOAC (10 ml) were refluxed for 2 hr, cooled and poured into cold water and the solids, after drying, were crystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE 1

	Arylidene derivatives				Tetrabromo compounds			
	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Bromine	
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
H	75	172	13.32	13.27	50	197	39.72	39.90
<i>p</i> -Cl	70	224	11.49	11.61	55	218	—	—
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O-	75	221	11.68	11.81	50	218	37.35	37.12
<i>p</i> -Br	60	213	10.31	10.00	40	202	49.36	50.00
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	65	219	11.36	11.18	50	236	35.59	35.87
<i>o</i> -Cl	70	> 250	11.50	11.61	46	186	—	—
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	60	> 225	11.09	11.18	45	185	35.61	35.87
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	55	> 250	11.20	11.26	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2

	Arylidene derivatives				Tetrabromo compounds			
	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Bromine	
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
H	65	212	13.18	13.27	60	192	39.61	39.90
<i>p</i> -Cl	62	> 250	11.42	11.61	60	220	—	—
<i>p</i> -Br	45	> 250	10.31	10.00	40	243	50.13	50.00
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	50	> 250	11.52	11.18	65	> 250	35.60	35.87
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O-	65	226	11.39	11.81	65	185	37.26	37.12
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	56	222	11.01	11.18	50	189	35.38	35.87
<i>o</i> -Cl	60	> 250	11.56	11.61	55	191	—	—
<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N	45	250	11.16	11.26	—	—	—	—

Tetrabromo derivatives from bis-arylidene thiazolidone (Table 1)

A solution of bis-arylidene derivatives (0.01*M*) in chloroform was treated with bromine (0.01*M*) in chloroform at 0° and the product isolated according to Rout *et al.*².

*Bis-arylidene thiohydantoin*s (Table 2)

Thiohydantoin (0.01*M*), aldehyde (0.01*M*), anhydrous NaOAc (0.05*M*) in HOAc (10 ml) were heated under reflux for 2 hr. After cooling it was diluted with water and the solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid.

Tetra bromo derivatives (Table 2)

A solution of bis-arylidene compounds (0.01*M*) in chloroform was treated with bromine in chloroform

and the deep red solid was isolated according to Rout *et al.*².

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. M. K. Rout, Principal, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack for his guidance, and Sambalpur University for a financial help to one of them (T.E.A.).

References

1. H. D. TRAUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1948, **70**, 3436.
2. M. K. ROUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1955, **77**, 2427.